

Unraveling multiphase conversion pathways in Li-S batteries through cryo-TEM and ML-assisted *operando* small-angle neutron scattering

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Abstract

Understanding the complex physicochemical processes in conversion-type batteries requires investigations across multiple length scales. Here, we present a novel approach to examine Li-S batteries at the nanoscale by combining cryogenic transmission electron microscopy (cryoTEM) with *operando* small-angle neutron scattering (SANS). CryoTEM revealed discharge products with a biphasic structure, consisting of nanocrystalline Li_2S within an amorphous Li_2S_x matrix. Data analysis of complementary *operando* SANS measurements was accelerated by a convolutional neural network trained to predict scattering curves based on plurigaussian random fields, enabling comprehensive parameter space exploration for model fitting. Our findings are in line with disproportionation-driven deposition of Li_2S_2 particles that agglomerate and partially reduce to Li_2S via solid-state conversion. This challenges the conventional view of direct, step-wise electroreduction of polysulfides at the electrode-electrolyte interface. Overall, our multi-technique approach demonstrates the value of combining localized high-resolution imaging with time-resolved *operando* scattering measurements to understand complex electrochemical conversion pathways in next-generation energy storage systems.

Introduction

As the world transitions to renewable power production to mitigate the growing climate crisis, batteries emerge as pivotal for electric mobility and stationary energy storage. Emerging technologies beyond lithium-ion batteries promise enhanced energy density and reduced environmental impact from raw materials. Among these, conversion-type systems, including metal-air (Me-Air)¹, metal-sulfur (Me-S) batteries², emerge as promising alternatives.

Despite their potential, conversion-type batteries face common challenges that hinder their practical adoption. These challenges include poor ionic/electronic conductivity and charge transfer kinetics and large volume changes of active materials, as well as (partially) dissolved reaction products causing side reactions and suboptimal active material utilization, all of which constrain cycling rates, cycle life, and energy density^{1,3-5}. Further progress is limited by a lack of understanding of the complex structural transitions and physicochemical processes, particularly at the nanometer scale⁶⁻¹⁰. The sulfur-to-sulfide conversion process in liquid-electrolyte lithium-sulfur (Li-S) batteries exemplifies these challenges. During discharge, crystalline sulfur (S_8) is reduced to crystalline lithium sulfide (Li_2S) through multiple soluble polysulfide intermediates (Li_2S_8 , Li_2S_6 , Li_2S_4 , etc.). This solid-liquid-solid conversion process is critical for battery performance as it dictates active material utilization and side reactions. However, the details of these processes remain unclear. Recent studies have shown that the complex nano- and microstructures of solid discharge products can consist of several phases (Figure 1a), and do not fit traditional nucleation and growth models, leaving many aspects of the conversion mechanism unresolved¹¹⁻¹⁷. To address this, advanced techniques are needed to probe sulfur-to-sulfide phase evolution at atomic and nanometer scales.

Current techniques for studying conversion mechanisms at the atomic- and nanoscale can be categorized into two groups: integral (or bulk) methods — including Raman, X-ray absorption spectroscopy, and both small and wide-angle scattering — and local techniques, such as electron microscopy. Integral methods give insights into the ensemble-averaged structural and chemical composition of the electrode at a given time. Conducting such measurements *operando* can yield a detailed picture of the structural and chemical changes during cycling^{6,14-16,18-24}. In the case of scattering measurements, the data analysis relies heavily on the chosen model, leading to potential variations in the interpretations drawn from the same dataset^{15,25,26}. Consequently, the process is susceptible to significant user bias, as the model selection can influence the conclusions reached. Microscopy techniques, on the other hand, offer model-free, localized chemical and structural insights. However, their utility is constrained by a limited field of view and the requirement for specialized cell designs for *in situ* measurements²⁷⁻³². Additionally, the need for ultra-high vacuum conditions and the electron beam-induced damage imposes significant limitations, particularly for materials like sulfur or lithium sulfide that are sensitive to such conditions³³.

In this work, we present a novel methodological approach for investigating conversion-type batteries at the nanoscale, combining advanced microscopy and scattering techniques with machine learning-enhanced data analysis (Figure 1b). We demonstrate this approach using Li-S batteries as a prototypical system, leveraging the synergistic properties of transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and small angle neutron scattering (SANS). We investigate discharge products

in Li-S battery cathodes using *ex-situ* energy filtered TEM (EFTEM) and electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) under cryogenic conditions to mitigate beam-induced damage. Air sensitivity is addressed using a vacuum-transfer cryo holder (VTC), and beam sensitivity is assessed under both non-cryogenic and cryogenic conditions^{33,34}.

To expedite the curve fitting process and allowing for a broader parameter space exploration in SANS data analysis, we employ machine learning algorithms. We train a convolutional neural network (forwardCNN) to predict SANS intensity curves based on input parameters of the plurigaussian random field (PGRF) model, reducing computational time by three orders of magnitude. This significant speed-up enables the application of Bayesian optimization for efficient determination of optimal PGRF parameters.

Our results reveal that the discharge product in Li-S battery cathodes comprises multiple solid phases, including nanocrystalline Li₂S embedded in an amorphous polysulfide matrix. Real-time structural data indicate that these phases do not change their mean size simultaneously during cycling, offering new insights into the electrochemical conversion mechanisms. This study further showcases the potential of combining advanced imaging and scattering techniques with computational analysis to study a variety of battery chemistries with complex conversion mechanisms.

Figure 1 Multi-scale analysis of deposition processes in conversion-type batteries using complementary techniques. a) Schematic illustrating the hierarchical structure of a conversion-type cathode (here Li-S battery), from the macro-scale electrode to the nanoscale multi-phase discharge product. b) Complementary characterization methods: Small angle neutron scattering (SANS) for operando structural evolution studies and electron microscopy for high-resolution imaging of the electrode morphology and composition.

Results and Discussion

CryoTEM

Previous works investigating Li-S cathodes have employed different strategies to mitigate beam and low-pressure-induced changes to the sample. Most notable are encapsulations of sulfur in hollow carbon structures for solid-state Li-S batteries or the usage of liquid cell holders to measure electrochemical TEM^{13,27,28,32,35}. While these methods yield deep insight into the local processes during (de-)lithiation, the carbons and cell geometry of such nanobatteries differ greatly from standard cells. Here, the *ex-situ* TEM sample was prepared by discharging a catholyte solution of 0.5 M Li_2S_8 and 1 M LiTFSI + 0.4 M LiNO_3 in diethylene glycol dimethyl ether (diglyme, 2G) onto a binder-free Ketjenblack (KB) powder (Figure 2a). The use of the commercial high-surface-area carbon black KB ensured comparability between the investigated structures and the structures found in standard Li-S battery cathodes. The discharge curve revealed a distinct plateau at 2.1 V vs. Li/Li^+ , indicating the formation of Li_2S onto the KB powder (Figure 2b). After full discharge, the powder was vacuum-dried without washing, ground with a mortar, and then transferred onto a Lacey Carbon TEM grid in an inert argon atmosphere (Figure 2c). By omitting the washing steps, we avoid the risk of removing easily soluble compounds (such as higher-order polysulfides Li_2S_x , $x > 1$) and altering the structure of the discharge product¹⁴. Figure S4 shows the washing impact of different solvents on the structure. Next, the grid was loaded on the LN2 Vacuum Transfer Holder by MelBuild (Figure 2d) and transported under Ar atmosphere from the glove box to the TEM (Figure 2e). The holder was then cooled to -193°C by introducing liquid nitrogen (LN2) into the holder's dewar. A more comprehensive description of the experimental procedure is provided in the methods section.

Figure 2 Cryo-TEM sample preparation and analysis workflow. A discharged cathode containing Ketjenblack carbon and Li_2S_8 catholyte is ground into a powder inside an Ar-filled glovebox. The sample is transferred to a TEM grid via direct immersion and loaded onto a vacuum-transfer cryo holder, which maintains inter conditions during transport to the microscope. In the TEM, the sample is investigated using high-resolution imaging (HRTEM) and spectroscopic measurements like EFTEM and TEM-EELS

The measurements were conducted in TEM mode because of the low Z-contrast between sulfur and carbon in STEM mode (Figure S1b). Avoiding STEM further helped mitigate damage induced by the highly condensed electron beam. The mortared cathode particles on the TEM grid differ a lot in size. One such typical particle comprised of KB and discharge products is displayed in Figure 3a. The discharge particles range from a few dozen to hundreds of nanometers in size, consistent with previous SEM observations^{14,36}. We focused on discharge material at the edge of the larger particle to get an unobscured view of its structure. High-resolution micrographs of the discharge products, taken under both ambient and cryogenic conditions (Figure 3b, c and S1 c-

f), demonstrate that the samples remained stable regardless of temperature. The discharge products are made of two distinct solid phases - a nanocrystalline and an amorphous one. The nanocrystalline phase can be assigned to Li_2S based on the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) showing spots which can be assigned to the 111, 200, 220, and 222 planes (inset in Figure 3b, c, and in Figure S1 in large).

There are four candidates for the amorphous phase, based on the chemical composition of the battery: the salt LiTFSI, the solvent 2G, Li_2S , or a higher order LiPS . LiTFSI salt is visible throughout the sample, as the cathode was not washed. However, the micrometer-sized salt particles are clearly identifiable by their strong contrast and crystallinity (Figure S1f, g). Next, we turn to EELS measurements to get a deeper understanding of the elements present. While the discharge product was stable under both ambient and cryogenic conditions for the HRTEM measurements, it degraded in under 1 sec during cryo-STEM EELS measurements, likely due to the increased local e^- -dose. We, therefore, turned towards cryo-TEM-EELS and cryo-EFTEM, sacrificing the local resolution of the elemental distribution. The e^- -dose were roughly $200 \text{ e}/\text{\AA}^2$ for EFTEM and up to $267 \text{ e}/\text{\AA}^2$ for STEM per frame. The discharge product in Figure 3d was measured at different energy levels and locations. The circles indicate the field-of-view during the TEM-EELS measurement, and their colors relate to the low- and core-loss spectrum shown in Figure 3e. The low-loss spectrum in blue shows a distinctive double peak plasmon feature (15.5 and 19.7 eV) that can be attributed to Li_2S ^{27,28}. The red curve shows a reference spectrum of Li_2S_x taken from Yang et al²⁸. The core-loss spectrum (yellow), acquired from the discharge product and supporting carbon structure, reveals two significant edges: sulfur (159 eV) and carbon (284 eV). Notably, the sulfur edge appears at lower energy compared to bulk sulfur (165 eV), consistent with previous reports for Li_2S ^{27,28,32}. The absence of nitrogen (402 eV) and oxygen (532 eV) edges further suggests that the amorphous phase consists of other amorphous Li_2S or an amorphous solid Li_2S_x (LiPS) phase. LiTFSI and residual 2G, both rich in oxygen and nitrogen, can be excluded as constituents of the amorphous phase.

While EELS can typically differentiate between Li_2S and polysulfides, particularly in the low-loss region²⁸, our lack of STEM's local resolution prevents direct distinction without sample alteration. To address this limitation, we acquired a series of EFTEM micrographs with energies filtered around 13, 17, and 21 eV (Figure 3f). Insets in the micrographs show a detailed view of the low-loss EELS spectrum of Li_2S and Li_2S_x . The low-loss spectrum remains unaltered after isolating and subtracting the zero-loss peak (Figure S2a, b), which suggests the sample to be sufficiently thin for any brightness differences to arise from chemical composition rather than thickness variations. The first two micrographs, centered around the Li_2S peaks (13 and 17 eV), reveal two distinct brightness regions: a brighter phase in the inner region, surrounded by a darker phase in the outer areas. At higher energies (21 eV), this brightness difference disappears, making the particle appear as a single phase. These findings indicate that the amorphous phase covering the particle must be a solid Li_2S_x . Consequently, the solid discharge product in Li-S batteries comprises nanocrystalline Li_2S embedded within amorphous Li_2S_x , which is in line with our previous study combining Raman spectroscopy with neutron and X-ray scattering¹⁴.

Figure 3 Multi-technique TEM analysis of discharged Li-S battery cathode. a) Overview of a typical cathode region with discharge particles highlighted in green (cryo-TEM). b, c) Fourier filtered and magnified views of a two-phase discharge particle under ambient and cryogenic conditions, respectively. Insets show FFT spots assigned to (111), (200), (220), and (222) planes of Li_2S crystals. d) High-resolution image of a two-phase discharge product (Fourier filtered). The blue, yellow and grey circles indicate the measurement area for the corresponding TEM-EELS spectrum in e). The blue curve shows the characteristic Li_2S double peak in the low-loss region. The sulfur edge onset (yellow) appears at 159 eV. Reference spectra for Li_2S_x (red)²⁸ and carbon structure (grey) are overlaid. f) EFTEM series centered around the Li_2S double-peak energies. The energy window for every micrograph is overlaid on the bottom right. Two distinct phases are visible at the double peak energies (13 ± 3 eV, 17 ± 3 eV), but the intensity difference diminishes at higher energy (21 ± 3 eV).

Machine Learning Enhanced *Operando* SANS

Next, we turn towards *operando* small angle neutron scattering (SANS) to further understand the biphasic discharge product and its behavior during galvanostatic cycling. For *operando* SANS measurements we installed a custom-built *operando* SANS cell at the D22 beamline at ILL Grenoble (Figure 4a)^{14,24}. A neutron beam of about 10 mm in diameter hit the Li metal, separator and the Li-S battery cathode. Control experiments ensured that we observed changes in the Li-S battery cathode only¹⁴. We used a battery chemistry equivalent to the one we used for cryoTEM measurements, using a free-standing sulfur infiltrated KB composite electrode (KB/S) with PTFE binder and 1 M LiTFSI + 0.4 M LiNO₃ in 2G as electrolyte. The 2G solvent is deuterated to achieve a scattering length density ($SLD_{el} = 5.63 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) that approximately matches the carbon's scattering length density ($SLD_c = 6.67 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) with a slight mismatch of 15.6%. The square of the SLD difference between active materials and both electrolyte/carbon is about 30 times higher than the square of the carbon-electrolyte SLD difference. This ensures that any variations in the SANS curves are predominantly due to changes in the nanostructure of the discharge products, as depicted in the sketch in Figure 4b.

The galvanostatic dis-/charge curves, shown in Figure 4c, reveal the standard features of Li-S batteries with ether-based electrolytes: (i) a high voltage plateau around 2.3 – 2.4 V corresponding to the dissolution of sulfur and its electrochemical reduction into polysulfides (Li₂S₈), followed by (ii) a second plateau above 2.0 V, which marks the coexistence of dissolved polysulfides and solid discharge products like Li₂S and (iii) a charging plateau above 2.2 V vs Li/Li⁺³⁷. Prior to discharge, the SANS curve reflects the constant contribution from the separator, PTFE binder, and carbon black due to imperfect SLD matching between deuterated electrolyte and carbon. The constant background at higher scattering vector q originates from incoherent scattering and the electrolyte, carbon structure, and sulfur structure factor. During discharge, the overall SANS intensity increases, and two distinct features (intensity shoulders) emerge at low and high q , stemming from the nanostructure of the solid discharge products (Figure 4d). During charging, the SANS intensity goes down again (Figure 4e). The contour plot in Figure 4f reveals the relative intensity change (normalized by the SANS intensity prior to discharge) as a function of time and q ; the shoulders in Figure 3d, e appear as intensity maxima. The intensity increase, indicative of the solid discharge product formation, starts with the onset of the lower voltage plateau. During charging, the overall intensity decreases, and the high- q intensity maximum shifts towards lower q -values. The position of low- q and high- q intensity shoulders at around (1) 0.2 nm^{-1} and (2) 1.5 nm^{-1} suggest structures with feature sizes of around $2\pi/0.2 \text{ nm}^{-1} \approx 30 \text{ nm}$ and $2\pi/1.5 \text{ nm}^{-1} \approx 4 \text{ nm}$, respectively. During charging, the high- q shoulder shifts slightly towards the lower q , and both features decrease in intensity until they vanish completely (Figure 4e). A similar behavior was previously reported under different experimental settings with small angle neutron and x-ray scattering^{14,19}.

To identify the origin of the high- q intensity shoulder, we performed small- and wide-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS/WAXS) measurements on discharged KB/S electrodes (Figure S3). The WAXS data revealed the expected diffraction peaks of nanocrystalline Li₂S (peaks (111) and (200)) in the discharged electrode. After washing the discharged electrode with diglyme, the Li₂S diffraction peak remained, while the high- q SAXS feature disappeared - unlike in the unwashed sample. This

suggests that the high- q feature observed in the SANS data corresponds to the soluble Li_2S_x phase seen in TEM. Based on our SAXS/WAXS analysis, previous Raman spectroscopy results, and other theoretical and experimental studies, we propose that this Li_2S_x phase is an amorphous, particulate Li_2S_2 phase^{12–14,38}. Hence, the low- q and high- q intensity shoulders observed in Figure 4d-f, along with the cryoTEM results, indicate that the nanostructure comprises larger Li_2S aggregates (around 30 nm, associated with the low- q shoulder) and an amorphous nanoparticulate Li_2S_2 phase (feature size around 4 nm, associated with the high- q shoulder). These Li_2S aggregates consist of individual crystallites with an average size of 14 nm, as confirmed by both Scherrer analysis (Figure S3c) and direct TEM observation (Figure 3b,c). This structural composition is the base assumption for the following *operando* SANS data modelling approach.

Figure 4 Operando SANS results and machine-learning supported data analysis pipeline. a) Sketch of SANS cell configuration and experimental setup at ILL. b) Differences in scattering length densities (SLD) visualized for the different materials. The SLD of the electrolyte was matched to the carbon using a deuterated solvent. c) (Dis-)charge profile of operando cell. The discharge and charge cycles are color-coded blue and red, respectively. d) Integrated intensity curve acquired during the discharge cycle and e) charge cycle, with color opacity indicating the state of (dis-)charge (SoDC, SOC). f) The two intensity shoulders are highlighted by plotting the relative intensity and marked as (1) for low-q and (2) for high-q. g) The Plurigaussian Random Fields function takes in 10 structural parameters and outputs a 3-phased stochastic structure with the corresponding small angle scattering intensity curve. h) CryoTEM data guides initial model selection and helps constraining initial PGRF parameter ranges and model selection. A pre-trained CNN predicts SANS intensity curves based on input parameters, which are then compared to experimental data. A Bayesian optimization algorithm refines parameter selection based on the error, iterating until convergence or a set iteration number. Final PGRF parameters for each state of charge are used to generate stochastic 3D representations of the electrode structure. This workflow combines structural insights from cryoTEM with machine learning techniques to efficiently analyze SANS data and reconstruct the evolving electrode nanostructure.

Machine Learning for the Plurigaussian random field (PGRF) model

CryoTEM revealed that the discharge product consists of at least two solid phases. To extract the nanoscale structural evolution of the two-phase solid discharge products from the *operando* SANS experiment, we chose the Plurigaussian random field (PGRF) model^{14,39,40}. This stochastic structural model effectively generates a small-angle scattering curve and a statistically representative real-space structure composed of three distinct phases: nanocrystalline Li₂S, the surrounding amorphous particulate Li₂S₂ phase, and the electrolyte (Figure 4g).

The PGRF model employs 13 input variables: 10 structural parameters that define the structures geometry and 3 material parameters representing the scattering length densities (SLDs) of the constituent materials. These inputs are used to calculate the corresponding scattering curve, effectively creating a Fourier transform of the scattering length density correlation function of the real-space physical structure. More details are explained in our recent study, in the methods section and in Gommès et al.⁴⁰. Figure S5 visualizes the concept. We implemented the functions in Python 3, accessible on GitHub⁴¹. In this performance-optimized version, the calculation of a single scattering curve takes approximately 2.4 seconds on our system. While this might seem fast, applying a curve fit to our measurement data with a widely unrestricted parameter space would still take several months.

To overcome this computational challenge, we turned to machine learning (Figure 4h). We trained a convolutional neural network which we call forwardCNN, to predict the SANS curve based on the input parameters of the PGRF function. Choosing the right structural stochastic model and parameter range requires apriori information on the expected nanostructure from cryoTEM measurements. The cryoTEM results indicated two solid discharge products in the nanometer range, for which the PGRF model is ideal. The experimental SANS intensities are then fitted by minimizing the error between the CNN-predicted SANS intensity and the experimental SANS intensity using Bayesian optimization. Once the PGRF parameters with the minimum error are found, a stochastically representative real-space model can be calculated.

Convolutional neural networks, commonly used in image recognition, are particularly effective at identifying patterns in complex data⁴². In our case, the network learns to recognize how changes in the PGRF parameters affect the resulting scattering curve. For training, we generated 250'000 SANS intensity/input parameters sets using the PGRF model (Figure 4g). The input parameters for the PGRF model varied over a broad range, covering any realistic three-phase nanostructure

with feature sizes from 0.5 to about 50 nm (for details, see methods and SI). The base structure and the training results of our forwardCNN are shown in Figure S8-15. The model achieves high precision, with an average mean squared error $< 10^{-5}$ on the intensity-normalized dataset, while taking only 25 ms per prediction. This represents a speed-up of three orders of magnitude compared to the traditional calculation method. A more detailed performance analysis, as well as an alternative model (inverseCNN) that predicts the PGRF parameters directly from the SAS curve is given in the SI. Combining the forwardCNN with Bayesian optimization is particularly advantageous: the forwardCNN provides flexibility, accurately predicting SANS curves even when some input (fitting) parameters are held constant, while Bayesian optimization excels at navigating the complex, non-convex parameter space of the PGRF function. The result is a powerful, machine learning-enhanced optimization loop that can fit a single curve in about 4 minutes, testing 10,000 different parameter combinations. This speed and efficiency open up new possibilities for real-time analysis and interpretation of SANS data during experiments and offer new opportunities to study dynamic processes in battery materials.

Fitting Results

Figure 5 illustrates the experimental and fitting process a-d and the retrieved parameter sets for every curve (e-l). The electrochemical cycle in Figure 5a is divided into the discharging (blue) and charging (red) segments. The first plateau at 2.4 V corresponds to the dissolution and conversion of sulfur to higher-order polysulfides (Li_2S_x , $6 \leq x \leq 8$). Solid discharge products, consisting of Li_2S_2 and Li_2S , are formed at the second plateau around 2.1 V. As the SANS experiment is only sensitive to the solid discharge products, we fit the scattering curves starting with the onset of the second plateau. The fitted curves in Figure 5b, c (blue and red) closely match the *operando* SANS curves (grey). This strong agreement is further supported by the normalized mean squared error shown in Figure 5d. The error increases significantly at the beginning and end of the cycle, which is when signal intensity and contrast are lowest due to the absence of discharge products.

To gain deeper insights into the structural evolution during cycling, we examined the PGRF parameters obtained from each fit, as shown in the lower panels of Figure 5e-l. We pre-selected eight out of the ten structural parameters based on a parameter study shown in Figure S6, which demonstrates the impact of each parameter on the structure. To explore the robustness and flexibility of our approach, we conducted two fitting rounds. In the first round, all eight pre-selected parameters were allowed to vary freely. The results revealed that only six parameters in Figure 5e-j showed a time-dependent trend, while the other two in Figure 5k-l oscillated around constant values. In a second fitting round, the two oscillating parameters were fixed at their mean values, which significantly reduced the noise in the remaining parameters without substantially affecting the overall fit quality. As highlighted by the parameter study in Figure S6, changes in the volume ratio (Figure 5l) appear to have correlated effects on the SANS intensity like the parameters V/V_{max} and $\phi_{\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2}$. When the volume ratio was allowed to vary, these parameters showed increased noise, suggesting an overextension of the Bayesian fitting algorithm. This interpretation is further supported by the inverse CNN model (Figure S15), which similarly struggled to accurately predict the volume ratio from the scattering curves. Overall, this two-step fitting process demonstrates the flexibility of the model fit to any number of fitting parameters while the trained

CNN remains the same. It allows for a systematic fitting procedure and identifies strongly correlated fitting parameters or parameter degeneracy.

Analyzing the key parameter trends in Figure 5g-e reveals important insights. The normalized volume of solid discharge products increases approximately linearly with time during discharge and decreases linearly with time during charge (Figure 5e). Notably, while the Li_2S aggregate size (approx. 2.5 times l_V in Figure 5g) increases during discharge and decreases during charge, the Li_2S_2 particle size (approx. 2.5 times l_Z in Figure 5h) remains constant during discharge and increases during charging¹⁴. This observation aligns with the q-shift of the high-q intensity shoulder in Figure 4f, indicating the Li_2S_2 structural evolution. As the volume factor parameter in Figure 5l was held constant, the volume ratio between Li_2S and Li_2S_2 was also fixed in our model. However, the overall volume fraction of Li_2S and Li_2S_2 with respect to the surrounding pore space changes slightly, as shown in Figure 5j. Figures 5m-p reveal the statistically representative real-space structures of the discharge product, calculated from the PGRF approach with the corresponding fitting parameter results at 50% discharged, 100% discharged, 50% charged, and 90% charged states, as an input. These 3D real-space cross-sections visualize the significant structural evolution of the Li_2S and Li_2S_2 phases throughout the cycling process and reflect the parameter changes discussed above.

Our structural analysis reveals a complex conversion process involving metastable intermediate phases, such as solid Li_2S_2 , which can persist even at the end of discharge. Therefore, explanations of galvanostatic discharge/charge profiles based solely on equilibrium phase diagrams³⁷ may be insufficient. Considering kinetics and metastable phases seems necessary to fully grasp electrochemical sulfur conversion.

We further compared our results from the SANS model fit with the experimental electrochemical data. In particular, we calculated capacities from the found Li_2S and Li_2S_2 fractions and compared them to capacities obtained from the electrochemical signal (Figure 5q). The dashed line represents the capacity evolution assuming complete conversion of sulfur to Li_2S and Li_2S_2 and taking the found $\text{Li}_2\text{S}/\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2$ volume fractions ($\phi_{\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2}$ and $\phi_{\text{Li}_2\text{S}}$) as an input. This SANS model result closely matches the electrochemical capacity at 100% state of discharge (SoDC, mismatch <1%). The capacity values calculated from the electrode's deposit volume V (derived from V/V_{max} in Figure 5q) multiplied by the Li_2S_2 and Li_2S volume fractions ($\phi_{\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2}$ and $\phi_{\text{Li}_2\text{S}}$) exceeds the experimental value by approximately 35% (solid line in Figure 5m). Possible sources of error include (i) a slight error in the absolute intensity calibration, (ii) a minor deviation from the nominal electrode diameter (e.g., a few percent deviation from 13 mm could significantly impact calculations), or (iii) Inhomogeneous $\text{Li}_2\text{S}/\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2$ deposition across the electrode.

Figure 5 Evolution of Plurigaussian Random Field parameters over a full discharge-charge cycle. Results from two fitting rounds are shown: one with 8 varying parameters (dashed lines) and another with 6 (solid lines). a) Discharge profile color-coded for the discharge (blue) and charge (red) cycle. b, c) Experimental SANS data (grey) with fitted curves overlaid in color. d) Corresponding fit error values. e) Intensity constant, indicating the amount of deposited material. f, g) Particle size evolution of Li_2S and Li_2S_2 , respectively. h, i) Porod constant and d_z parameter, showing visible trends over the cycle. j) Volume fraction of Li_2S_2 in the discharge product. k, l) Beta angle and the volume factor oscillated around constant values and were fixed in the second fitting iteration. m-p) PGRF cross-section and volumes for a given state of charge generated using the fitted parameters. q) Correlation between capacity measured

electrochemically (crosses) and capacity derived from the PGRF model using two different approaches: absolute intensity/deposition volume (solid line) and volume fraction (dashed line).

A holistic data interpretation

It is crucial to merge the complementary information obtained from cryoTEM and *operando* SANS results (Figure 6a). By relating the fitted parameters from *operando* SANS to electrochemical data and the phase distribution observed in cryoTEM, we can build a comprehensive understanding of the sulfur conversion mechanism. CryoTEM reveals two key observations: (1) Li_2S forms crystallites up to 10 nm in size, which aggregate into larger structures, and (2) these Li_2S aggregates are embedded in an amorphous Li_2S_x phase, which is likely Li_2S_2 . This aligns with SANS model results, indicating a composite structure of Li_2S aggregates (of approx. 30 nm in size) and an amorphous nanostructured Li_2S_2 phase (with feature sizes up to 4 nm). The evolution of these phases during discharge and charge is crucial for understanding the reaction mechanism. The volume fraction of solid discharge products shows a positive correlation with capacity during discharge as phases are formed, and decreases during charge as they dissolve (Figure 5e). While the Li_2S aggregate size steadily increases during discharge and decreases during charge, the Li_2S_2 feature size remains constant during discharge and increases during charge (Figure 5f, g). Our findings align with computational studies predicting a stable solid phase of Li_2S_2 and its favorable formation pathway from Li_2S_4 ^{43,44}. A recent *in-situ* TEM study has provided direct evidence for transient Li_2S_2 and amorphous lithium polysulfide deposits, further supporting our outcomes^{13,38}.

Based on these insights, we propose a sulfur-to-sulfide conversion mechanism as illustrated in Figure 6b. Crystalline sulfur is reduced to dissolved polysulfides, such as Li_2S_8 or Li_2S_6 , which are further reduced to Li_2S_4 . As seen by X-ray absorption and Raman spectroscopy, dissolved Li_2S_4 tends to disproportionate into Li_2S_6 and Li_2S_2 in ether-based electrolytes^{14,45}, leading to the formation of larger Li_2S_2 aggregates via precipitation from solution. This process aligns with two key experimental observations: (1) The size of the larger aggregates is significantly influenced by the applied current or overpotential, which can be explained by classical nucleation and growth mechanisms^{36,46,47}; (2) The feature size of the Li_2S_2 nanostructure (approx. 4 nm) remains the same across various systems and experimental conditions, likely due to local transport limitations during the disproportionation reaction^{14,15,19}. Once the Li_2S_2 nanostructure is formed, it is partially reduced to Li_2S through electroreduction. We hypothesize that mass transport for this solid-state reaction occurs via interfaces in the Li_2S_2 nanostructure. Given that electroreduction requires a direct pathway between the carbon host and the formed Li_2S , we believe that the prevalence of the amorphous phase increases with distance from the carbon surface. While some of our TEM data suggest that more Li_2S is found in close proximity to the carbon host (Figure S1), a more in-depth analysis is required to confirm this mechanism. This fact could explain why Li-S batteries cannot reach their theoretical capacity.

Figure 6: Proposed formation mechanism of Li_2S/Li_2S_2 in nonaqueous lithium-sulfur batteries. a) Comparison of composite solid discharge products obtained with TEM and PGRF modelling / SANS. b) The schematic illustrates the stepwise reduction of polysulfides during discharge. Dissolved Li_2S_8 is initially reduced to shorter-chain polysulfides (Li_2S_x , $4 \leq x \leq 7$) near the carbon surface. Solid Li_2S_2 aggregates precipitate from solution, likely through disproportionation (DISP) of Li_2S_4 . The Li_2S_2 particles subsequently undergo solid-state conversion to form Li_2S crystals. Such conversion would preferentially occur near the triple-phase boundary of carbon, electrolyte, and Li_2S_2 , resulting in a gradient of Li_2S fraction within the discharge product.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study establishes a comprehensive experimental framework for investigating the electrochemical phase transformation in conversion-type batteries, exemplified by lithium-sulfur batteries. By integrating cryoTEM/EELS for high-resolution structural and chemical exploration with machine learning-enhanced *operando* SANS for real-time statistical nanostructure analysis, we have developed an effective approach to understand electrochemical processes at the nanoscale.

Our cryoTEM and EELS investigations provided structural and chemical data, laying the groundwork for subsequent model selection and adaptation in *operando* SANS studies. The implementation of our forwardCNN significantly reduced the computation time of the SANS model fit based on stochastic modelling. This allowed us to explore a wide range of the parameter space and generate statistically representative real-space structures of complex three-phase nanostructures. By reducing the need for parameter constraints during the model fit, this method decreases user imposed restrictions and enables a detailed, quantitative analysis of nanostructure evolution during battery cycling.

A key finding of our methodology is the identification of a Li_2S / Li_2S_x biphasic discharge product in Li-S batteries. The consistency between cryoTEM and *operando* SANS results give evidence for a two-step mechanism involving Li_2S_2 precipitation from solution followed by solid-state electrochemical reduction to Li_2S . This mechanistic insight highlights the significance of real-time tracking of nanoscale phase evolution, allowing for a deeper understanding of the physicochemical mechanisms governing complex conversion-type battery systems.

The approach presented here not only elucidates the lithiation mechanism in Li-S batteries but also offers a versatile framework that can be applied to a broad range of conversion-type battery

chemistries and beyond. Our work underlines that next to thermodynamic equilibrium states³⁷ also the path to equilibrium, often complicated by metastable intermediate states, is crucial for understanding the properties of conversion-type battery systems.³⁷

Methods

Materials

For *operando* SANS measurements we used carbon/sulfur composite cathodes with a C/S mass-ratio of 1:1. The carbon was a carbon black material (Ketjenblack EC-600JD, sourced from ANR Technologies) with a Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) specific surface area of $1400 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and minimal metal contamination ($<30 \text{ ppm}$). For melt infiltration, we first mixed the carbon with elemental sulfur at the mass ratio of 1:1, manually with pestle and mortar for about 5 min. The prepared mixture was then melt-infiltrated at 155°C for 7-8 h in a sealed evacuated glass oven (Büchi, Switzerland). The final sulfur mass content was verified by weight.

To create free-standing electrodes, we combined the carbon/S composite with polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE, acquired as a 60% aqueous suspension from Sigma Aldrich) in a 90:10 mass ratio, using isopropanol ($\geq 99.8\%$, Sigma Aldrich) as a dispersant. The components were manually blended in a mortar for 10 minutes at room temperature (25°C). We then rolled the resulting paste into films of $180 \pm 10 \mu\text{m}$ thickness. These films underwent a cleaning process using a mixture of acetone ($\geq 99.5\%$, Sigma Aldrich) and deionized water ($18 \text{ M}\Omega\text{cm}$), followed by overnight vacuum drying at 120°C and 10 mbar pressure.

The deuterated electrolyte consisted of 1 M lithium bis(trifluoromethane)sulfonimide (LiTFSI, 99.95% trace metals basis), and 0.4 M lithium nitrate (LiNO_3 , 99.99% trace metals basis) dissolved in 100% deuterated diethylene glycol dimethyl ether (2G, anhydrous, 99.5%) from Cambridge Isotope Laboratories Inc.

The catholyte used for TEM investigations consisted of 0.5 M Li_2S_8 , 1 M LiTFSI, (99.95% trace metals basis), and 0.4 M LiNO_3 , 99.99% trace metals basis) dissolved in 2G (anhydrous, 99.5%).

For the electron microscopy sample preparation, we fabricated a binder-free cathode. To achieve that, we created a thick paste by mixing the carbon black powder with the catholyte at a ratio of 20 mg/50 μL . This paste was applied to a glassy carbon disc (SIGRADUR G Discs, 16 mm diameter, 0.5 mm thickness) and assembled in in-house-made coin-cell-type cells (uniaxial pressure of $0.7 \pm 0.1 \text{ MPa}$), utilizing a polyethylene (PE) separator (Targray, PE16A) and Whatman separator. We added 100 μL of extra catholyte to ensure proper wetting of the separators. The electrolyte-to-sulfur ratio (E/S) and electrolyte-to-carbon ratio (E/C) are 7.8 and 7.5 respectively.

To synthesize Li_2S_8 , we combined stoichiometric amounts of elemental sulfur (powder, 99.98% trace metals basis, Sigma Aldrich) and lithium metal (110 μm thick high-purity foil, FMC Lithium Corporation) in excess anhydrous tetrahydrofuran (THF, $\geq 99.9\%$, inhibitor-free, Sigma Aldrich). The THF underwent a multi-step drying process using Al_2O_3 and molecular sieves, followed by distillation. We verified the water content using Karl Fischer titration (Mettler Toledo C20), ensuring it remained below 2 ppm. The entire synthesis took place in an argon-filled glovebox with strictly controlled atmosphere (H_2O and $\text{O}_2 < 0.1 \text{ ppm}$). The mixture was heated to 50°C and stirred until complete dissolution occurred. Finally, we removed the THF under vacuum (10 mbar) to obtain the dry polysulfide powders.

Experimental Methods

Experimental *operando* small angle neutron scattering (SANS) experiments were conducted under galvanostatic discharge/charge conditions at the ILL's D-22 beamline, utilizing a wavelength of 0.5 nm and a 10 mm beam diameter⁴⁸. The setup included two areal detectors positioned at distances of 17.6 m and 1.4 m for an overlapping q-region. The custom two-electrode SANS cell¹⁴, consisted of a PEEK body and two aluminum elements contacting cathode and anode from the top and the bottom. 12 mm aluminum windows ensures enough transmission for incident and scattered Neutrons and uniform mechanical pressure. The cell stack comprised copper ($\geq 99.9\%$, Schlenk Metallfolien) and aluminum foil current collectors ($\geq 99.5\%$, Korf), a lithium metal anode ($\geq 99.9\%$, Alfa Aesar, 0.75 mm thickness, 16 mm diameter), a glass fibre separator (Whatman GF/A, 21 mm diameter), and a KB/S cathode with 13 mm in diameter, prepared according to the procedure above. The *operando* cell, with E/S and E/C are 38.3 and 31.3 respectively, was discharged at C/10. The neutron beam hit all cell components, with only the cathode showing reversible and notable structural changes. The 2D detector signals were azimuthally averaged, and corrected for empty cell scattering, and the detector dark current. Finally, the SANS intensities were normalized to absolute intensities (in cm^{-1}) using transmission correction, detector efficiency correction, D22 detector parallax correction and by dividing the data by the sample volume (assuming a sample thickness of 0.007 cm) and empty beam flux.

The *ex situ* SAXS/WAXS measurements (Figure S3) of the discharged KB/S cathode (galvanostatic discharge at C/10) were carried out at a laboratory SAXS/WAXS system (Xeuss 3.0 HR, Xenocs) using a copper microsource (with $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation), a 2D areal SAXS detector (Eiger 2R 1M, Dectris), and a 2D areal WAXS detector (Eiger 2R 500K, Dectris).

For TEM measurements, the cathode was prepared as described above. Next, the cell was discharged with C/20. After discharge, the cell was disassembled, and the KB was scratched off the GC disc. The KB flakes were subsequently dried under vacuum and ground into a fine powder using a mortar. This sample was then transferred to a Lacey Carbon Type-A Copper TEM grid (TedPella, Nr. 01890) by directly immersing the grid into the powder.

The different cycling rates (C/10 for SANS, C/20 for TEM) were chosen based on the requirements of each technique. The slower rate for TEM samples optimized the preparation of binder-free cathodes, ensuring better sample transfer and higher discharge capacity. Similarly, for cryo-TEM experiments, Li_2S_8 catholyte was used instead of sulfur-infiltrated cathodes to ensure precise control of the active material amount and enable good electronic contact in the binder-free cathodes, which was essential for proper sample transfer onto the TEM grid. This difference in starting materials does not affect the mechanistic interpretations, as elemental sulfur initially dissolves and converts to high-order polysulfides (Li_2S_8) before following the same reduction pathway with identical voltage responses at 2.1 V. The effect of slightly different cycling rates (C/20 vs. C/10) on the nanostructure is minor¹⁴.

The TEM grid was transferred under Ar atmosphere from the glovebox to the TEM using a double tilt LN2 vacuum transfer holder (VTC, MeiBuild) and Gatan 648 double tilt vacuum holder. TEM measurements were carried out on a double Cs-corrected JEOL GrandARM operated at 300 kV (ETH Zürich) and at 80/200kV on a double Cs-corrected JEOL JEM 2200fs (Philipps-Universität

Marburg). We followed two different LN2 cryo-vacuum-transfer-holder transfer procedures, depending on the microscope. For measurements on GrandARM it works as follows: First, the holder loaded with the TEM-grid was transferred from the glovebox to the TEM. Once the sample was inside the airlock of the TEM, the chamber was purged three times with nitrogen. During the third pumping cycle, the tip was extended into the airlock at an ion pump current of 200 μA . Alternatively, for measurements on JEM 2200fs, which is equipped with a diffusion instead of turbomolecular pump, the holder is first pre-pumped at a pumping a pumping station overnight. The tip is again extended during pumping. The next morning, the tip is retracted and the holder transferred to the microscope. In this case, the tip is extended into the airlock at the later stages of pumping. After the vacuum has stabilized, the holder is inserted into the column. In both cases, the holder was then cooled to -193°C by introducing liquid nitrogen (LN2) into the holder's dewar. To mitigate LN2 boiling and associated vibrations, helium gas was introduced into the cryo-container, further reducing the temperature to -198°C , at which point the bubbling ceased^{49,50}. The system was allowed to equilibrate for one hour, after which the LN2 was replenished and the helium gas cycle repeated. Following a second hour of stabilization, the system reached thermal equilibrium with a drift rate of approximately 1.5 nm/min, at which point data acquisition commenced. During the cryo-measurements, the tip was cooled down to -165°C to reduce drift.

Machine Learning and SANS Data Fitting

All simulations and fitting procedures were performed on a high-performance Linux-based system equipped with a 16-core AMD Threadripper PRO 5955WX processor (4 GHz), 64 GB DDR4 3200 MHz ECC memory, and an NVIDIA RTX 4090 GPU with 24 GB VRAM.

We implemented a custom CNN model using PyTorch to predict SANS intensity curves from input parameters. The architecture comprises three blocks, each containing one deconvolutional and two convolutional layers with ReLU activation functions, followed by max pooling. The network takes 8 input parameters and outputs a 117-point intensity curve. Dropout layers ($p = 0.5$) were inserted throughout the blocks to mitigate overfitting. A flattening layer was employed to generate the final 1D output. The model's trainable parameters totaled approximately 3 million. Adam with a learning rate of $8 \cdot 10^{-4}$ and at StepLR scheduler with a step size of 4 and gamma of 0.5 was chosen.

A dataset of 250,000 simulated Small Angle Scattering (SAS) curves was generated based on the Plurigaussian Random Field (PGRF) model. The parameter ranges used for simulation are detailed in Table S1. This dataset was partitioned into training (80%), validation (10%), and test (10%) subsets. Prior to training, we added the experimental background, applied logarithmic transformation to the intensity values and normalized the intensity value and all parameters to the [0, 1] interval based on their respective global minima and maxima. Training was conducted over 40 epochs with consistent batch sizes of 256 for train, 128 for validation and test subsets. This process was repeated for four times. For the fitting process, the four networks were combined and their prediction averaged.

Experimental data fitting was performed using the Optuna library, implementing a Bayesian optimization algorithm with mean squared error as the optimization metric. For handling the SANS intensity background at high q -values, we added the experimental background to the simulated

PGRF curves during CNN training rather than subtracting it from experimental data (we selected the background SANS curve at the point where all sulfur was dissolved and no other solid phases were present; Figure 4c, potential drop before onset of the second discharge plateau). This approach proved more robust as it improved the CNN's ability to recognize weak scattering features and enabled direct fitting to untreated scattering data (Figure S7). The experimental logarithmic intensity data underwent normalization based on the simulated dataset's minimum and maximum intensity values. Hence, all simulated SANS intensities are normalized between 0 and 1. This normalization approach is valid because our simulated dataset was designed to span the largest possible range of scattering curves, ensuring that the experimental data to be fitted falls within the boundaries established by the training set's intensity extremes. The optimization process evaluated 10,000 parameter combinations over a duration of 35 minutes.

The PGRF SANS model

In the following, we briefly describe the PGRF concept for calculating SANS intensities of a Li_2S - Li_2S_2 composite nanostructure, in line with recent works^{14,40}. Figure S5 summarizes the procedure. The experimental SANS intensity of the discharged cathode in absolute units (cm^{-1}) can be decomposed into two main components:

$$I(q) = I_{\text{Li}_2\text{S},\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2}(q) + BG. \quad (1)$$

$I_{\text{Li}_2\text{S},\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2}(q)$ corresponds to the scattering from the $\text{Li}_2\text{S}/\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2$ structure. BG accounts for the constant background intensity, primarily from incoherent scattering and the atomic structure factor of the electrolyte and carbon. Scattering from the carbon black nanostructure is negligibly small as the deuterated electrolyte approximately matches the scattering length density of the carbon.

The experimental SANS intensity of the $\text{Li}_2\text{S}/\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2$ nanostructure (in units of cm^{-1}) can be written as

$$I_{\text{Li}_2\text{S},\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2}(q) = V/V_{\text{max}} [A q^{-4} + I_{\text{PGRF}}(q)], \quad (2)$$

V/V_{max} is the relative volume of the deposited $\text{Li}_2\text{S}/\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2$ nanostructure and allows us to account for the changing deposit volume during cycling. V_{max} corresponds to the irradiated beam area (approx. 1 cm in diameter) times an effective $\text{Li}_2\text{S}/\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2$ deposit thickness d_{max} . We chose 0.007 cm as an initial estimate for d_{max} and used this value for the normalization to absolute intensities. The first term, $A q^{-4}$, describes the Porod decay from large $\text{Li}_2\text{S}/\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2$ agglomerates (larger than 100 nm, see Figure 3a and Figure S1), with the SANS intensity being proportional to q^{-4} within the measured q -range. The second term, $I_{\text{PGRF}}(q)$, models the nanostructure within the 1-50 nm range using plurigaussian random fields (PGRF).

The SANS intensity $I_{\text{PGRF}}(q)$ can be represented as the Fourier transform of the scattering length density (SLD) correlation function $C(r)$. This relationship is given by:

$$I_{\text{PGRF}}(q) = \int_0^\infty C(r) \frac{\sin(qr)}{qr} 4\pi r^2 dr. \quad (3)$$

For the three-phase system composed of Li_2S , Li_2S_2 , and Electrolyte, $C(r)$ can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
C(r) = & (\rho_{\text{Li}_2\text{S}} - \rho_{\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2})(\rho_{\text{Li}_2\text{S}} - \rho_{\text{EL}})[P_{\text{Li}_2\text{S}\text{Li}_2\text{S}}(r) - \phi_{\text{Li}_2\text{S}}^2] \\
& + (\rho_{\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2} - \rho_{\text{Li}_2\text{S}})(\rho_{\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2} - \rho_{\text{EL}})[P_{\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2}(r) - \phi_{\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2}^2] \\
& + (\rho_{\text{EL}} - \rho_{\text{Li}_2\text{S}})(\rho_{\text{EL}} - \rho_{\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2})[P_{\text{ELEL}}(r) - \phi_{\text{EL}}^2].
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

where, ρ_i denotes the scattering length density, ϕ_i the volume fraction and $P_{ii}(r)$ the two-point correlation function of phase i .

By employing Gaussian random fields (GRF), one can create a 3D model of a two-phase pore structure from the fit to an experimental scattering curve. Plurigaussian random fields (PGRF) extend this concept by combining two GRFs to model SANS intensities and 3D structures in three-phase systems. A GRF $Y(\mathbf{x})$ is defined as:

$$Y(\mathbf{x}) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{N}} \sum_{i=1}^N \cos(\mathbf{k}_i \cdot \mathbf{x} - \varphi_i), \tag{5}$$

and a corresponding two-point correlation function of the GRF is given by

$$g_Y(r) = \frac{1}{\cosh(r/l_Y)} \cdot \frac{\sin(2\pi r/d_Y)}{(2\pi r/d_Y)}, \tag{6}$$

where l_Y is a correlation length parameter related to the feature size of the structure, and d_Y characterizes ordering effects.

The power spectral density associated with $g_Y(r)$ can be written as

$$f_Y(k) = \frac{k}{\pi} l_Y d_Y \frac{\sinh(\pi k l_Y/2) \sinh(\pi^2 l_Y/d_Y)}{\cosh(\pi k l_Y) + \cosh(2\pi^2 l_Y/d_Y)}. \tag{7}$$

To generate a two-phase porous structure from the GRF, threshold values α are introduced. All points x for which $\alpha < Y(x) \leq \infty$ are assigned to the pore space (the combined $\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2 + \text{EL}$ phase), while other coordinates correspond to the Li_2S scaffold. The threshold α is linked to the Li_2S volume fraction $\phi_{\text{Li}_2\text{S}}$ by

$$\phi_{\text{Li}_2\text{S}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{\alpha}^{\infty} \exp\left(-\frac{t^2}{2}\right) dt. \tag{8}$$

For the three-phase system, a second independent GRF $Z(x)$ is generated sharing the same functional form of the correlation function but distinct parameters l_Z and d_Z . The Li_2S_2 phase is obtained by combining $Z(x)$ and $Y(x)$ and applying thresholds in the Y, Z partition plane (Figure S5):

$$\phi_{\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2} = \iint_{(Y,Z) \in D_{\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2}} \frac{1}{2\pi} \exp\left(-\frac{Y^2 + Z^2}{2}\right) dY dZ \tag{9}$$

The two-point correlation function for the Li_2S_2 phase is:

$$P_{\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2} = \int_{D_{\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2}} dY_1 dZ_1 \int_{D_{\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2}} dY_2 dZ_2 G_{g_Y(r)}(Y_1, Y_2) G_{g_Z(r)}(Z_1, Z_2) \quad (10)$$

These distributions are obtained using Hermite polynomials⁴⁰ (similar considerations apply for Li_2S). The corresponding scattering intensities can then be calculated from correlation functions using Equations 3 and 4. The morphology of the Li_2S_2 phase is influenced by the angle β and the $\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2/\text{EL}$ boundary line, as shown in Figure S5. When $\beta \rightarrow 0$, the Li_2S_2 phase forms a thin film perfectly coating the Li_2S phase. Conversely, when the $\text{Li}_2\text{S}_2/\text{EL}$ boundary is parallel to the Y-axis ($\beta \rightarrow \pi/2$), the Li_2S_2 (or EL) structure within the Li_2S pores becomes statistically independent of the Li_2S structure.

Data and Code Availability

The Python implementation of the PGRF algorithm and the machine learning models are openly available on GitHub (https://github.com/JeanvonMentlen/machine_learning_enhanced_pgrf). All raw experimental data and the PGRF dataset used to train the CNN have been deposited in Zenodo and are accessible at DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14532384](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14532384).

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Declaration of Interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, J-M.M., V.W. and C.P.; methodology, J-M.M., T.D., J.B., M.P., A.V., P.D., L.P. and C.P.; investigation, J-M.M., A.S.G., V.W. and C.P.; writing—original draft, J-M.M. and C.P.; writing—review & editing, J-M.M., A.S.G., T.D., J.B., M.P., A.V., L.P. and C.P.; funding acquisition, V.W., C.P. and A.V.; resources, K.V., V.W., C.P.; supervision, V.W. and C.P.

Supporting Information

Document S1. Figures S1-S13 and Table S1

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